

Speech Function In Insurance Advertising Slogans

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Abstract

The objectives of this study was to describe the types of speech function and the reasons of using them in the insurance advertising slogan. This research used descriptive qualitative research design. The data was taken from the insurance advertising slogans in the form of sentences that belonged to the types of speech function. To collect the data, the researcher used documentary technique. Based on the analysis of the data, it could be concluded that the types of speech function in the insurance advertising slogans can be classified into statement category. The reason of using speech function in the insurance advertising slogans was mostly used to persuade to readers or customers to join with the company despite of the speech functions of some advertisements which described its content.

Keywords: speech function, advertising, slogan

Introduction

In daily activities, people keep using language which serves a range of functions. It is usually adjusted to the social context in which the communication occurs. The functions of language can also be varied according to the purpose of the communication. This is to say that the

Halliday (1994:117), there are some reasons for using speech function, such as: descriptive (to describe factual information), evaluative (to make a value judgment), emotive (to express emotion), evocative (to evoke an emotional response in an audience), persuasive (to persuade someone to accept something), interrogative (to elicit information), directive (to tell someone to do something), performative (to describe verbs that describe actions carried out by speakers), and recreational (language is used for fun or enjoyment or telling of joke).

The study of speech function can be researched in advertisement. Advertising has become the part and parcel of present-day life. From everywhere around us, advertisements of diverse types attack our privacy. In spite of it, there is an attractive power, which is able to manipulate the consumer; an invisible voice of advertisement

advocates, encourages, asks, announces and deeply embeds into peoples' minds (Lapsanska, 2006). Thus, this study will study about the speech function used in slogan especially in insurance advertising.

Method

This research was conducted by using descriptive qualitative design. The sources of the data were all insurance advertisement downloaded from internet. The steps of collecting data were begun by downloading the advertisements. There were 20 advertisements used as the source of data were Allianz, Tugu Pratama Indonesia, Asuransi Bhakti Bhayangkara, Arthagraha General Insurance, Asuransi Maipark Indonesia, Asuransi Jasa Raharja Putera, Asuransi Reliance Indonesia, Maskapai Asuransi Sonwelis, Asuransi Raya, Berdikari Insurance, Asuransi Art Arindo, Asuransi Binagriya Upakara, Panpacific General Insurance, Asuransi Tugu Mandiri, Commonwealth Life, MNC Life Insurance, Maa General Assurance, Asuransi Prudential, Asuransi Jasa Tania, and Lippo Insurance. After gathering all the advertisements, the researcher selected the sentences that represented slogan. Then, the sentences were analyzed by following the theory of speech function by Halliday (1994:68) to find the categories used in speech function in insurance advertising along with the reasons for using it.

The data was analyzed by using interactive model of Miles & Huberman (2014:33), they were: data condensation, data display, and conclusion drawing/verification.

Results

Type of speech function in Insurance Advertising Slogans

Theoretically, Halliday (1994:68) states that speech function categorizes speech function into 4 types, such as: command, offer, statement, and question.

Practically, the speech function found in the advertisements was only the statement. Statement is a way of delivering information by stating in speech or writing. type as it can be seen from the data below:

Data 1

Always listening always understanding.

This slogan belongs to Prudential insurance company. The slogan above represented that they could give good services to the customer by explicitly state that they

always listen and understand. The slogan is categorized as statement because it merely described who they were, that was as a company that always listen and understand; even though the aim of the statement was to persuade the readers to buy their product.

The slogan that belonged to the speech function of statement occurred 20 times which was cited from 20 advertisements.

Reasons for using the speech function in insurance advertisements

In addition to the type of speech function used in the insurance advertisements, there were also two reasons found, such as: descriptive and persuasive.

Descriptive

Theoretically, descriptive reason is used to describe factual information. It is characterized by subject + finite. Practically, the descriptive reason of the use of speech function in the slogan occurred 9 times and it could be seen in this following data.

Data 2

Keluarga sehat menuju sejahtera

Asuransi Jasa Tania company had a slogan: *Keluarga sehat menuju sejahtera* was realized by the features Subject + Finite. The reasons of using speech function is descriptive. This can be seen from the using of the words in the slogan. The word *Keluarga sehat menuju sejahtera* was to describe that *Asuransi Jasa Tania* was an insurance company that prioritized the members to have healthy family.

Persuasive

Theoretically, persuasive reason of using speech act was used to persuade someone to accept something or to act in a certain way. Practically, persuasive reason in the slogan of insurance occurred 11 times out of 20 advertisements as one of the examples was realized in this following data.

Data 3

Your risk is our concern. Our protection is your solution.

Arthagraha General Insurance company had a slogan: “Your risk is our concern. The reasons of using speech function is persuasive. This can be seen from the sentences in the slogan. The word “Your risk is our concern. Our protection is your solution” was to present a point of view and to persuade a reader about Arthagraha General Insurance company that the customer’s risk was their concern and their protection was the customer’s solution. Thus, the company implicitly wanted to say that the readers did not

need to take a long time to think about it since they presented themselves as the solution for the readers.

Discussion

The findings of this study were: (a) the only type of speech function used in the insurance was statement, and (b) the reasons of using the statement speech function were to describe the insurance companies as well as to persuade the readers to join them. As compared with the study conducted by Martanto (2014) who studied about the speech functions in utterances used by *Alex Hitches* and *Sara Mendes*, he found that the dominant use of speech functions was statement followed by questions. From the study conducted by Martanto (2014) and the researcher, it could be concluded that speech acts could be varied according to the mode of the communication whether it was written or spoken one.

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